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EXTENDED-ABSTRACT

Design Citizenship: Reflections on the Value of Participatory Design in Cultivating Democratic Cultures in Design Projects with Children

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Figure 1: An example of methods used in our projects: Children reflecting what they had learned in different phases of a project

Abstract

Democracy is facing a crisis characterized by the erosion of fundamental rights. Children are not strangers to this new scenario, as they already face many online hostilities threatening diversity and inclusion in their everyday lives. We argue that democracy thrives with increased participation, and that children have a lot to say and expertise that needs to be acknowledged in society and in citizenship education in particular. We argue that Scandinavian participatory design and its principles—especially those that advocate for democratic methods, design as futures making, and children’s transformative agency fostered through computing education—can help cultivate democratic cultures and thus show great promise for children’s citizenship education linked with technology design and use. We introduce the concept of ‘design citizenship’ as a key concept to develop such pedagogy of hope, highlighting its potential through past critical design and technology projects with children in various learning environments.

CCS Concepts

• **Human-centered computing** → **Human computer interaction (HCI)**; **Empirical studies in HCI**;

Keywords

Participatory design, Children, Computing education, Citizenship education, Technology

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1 Introduction

In recent decades, the perception of a crisis of democracy has gained momentum as part of a global trend. While Europeans still prefer democratic values [30], researchers warn of democracy’s erosion and the shrinking European civic space, happening at various levels in member states. Scholars attribute this crisis to the rise of identity politics and the dissociation between liberalism and democracy [4, 14, 28], also known as ‘illiberal democracy’ or ‘undemocratic liberalism’ [28]. Western democracies, based on many exclusions, face numerous unresolved contradictions that call for examination and public debate. For instance, children and youth have been

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historically excluded from voting, which has traditionally been regarded as democracy’s hallmark mechanisms. However, many studies show that young people have a lot to say about the things that matter to them [27, 35]. Their current practices around shaping these matters should be appreciated and further cultivated, as participatory democracy is learned through participation [2].

Supporting active participation in society is central to citizenship education. While approaches to citizenship education vary, the overarching goal is to help individuals understand their societal roles, promote active participation, and encourage thoughtful consideration of citizenship rights and responsibilities [15]. We adopt a broad perspective on citizenship education, including the cultivation of values, attitudes, skills, aptitudes, and commitments, alongside knowledge acquisition and conceptual understanding [10, 29]. Scandinavian participatory design (PD) and its principles, which champion democratic ways of working [21]; design as futures making [9, 24]; and children’s transformative agency supported by computing education [6, 16, 19]; can contribute to cultivating democratic cultures through children’s citizenship education. Along these lines, we introduce the notion of ‘Design Citizenship’ and argue for its necessity in children’s citizenship education.

2 Background

In PD, democratic practices and workplace democracy have been core values from the start [3, 12]. In PD, cooperative work where everyone is heard and their skills and expertise are valued, is central [13, 25]. Genuine participation is the goal, recognizing all participants as legitimate contributors with valuable expertise to bring to the design process [25, 31]. Mutual reciprocal learning and competence development are emphasized, helping participants understand each other, find common ground, and develop skills to contribute [13]. PD prioritizes equalizing power relations, especially supporting those in marginalized or power-weak position are supported to have a voice and a say [13, 25]. Sensitivity to situational aspects is also central: design needs to be considered and be responsive to local circumstances [13, 25]. PD has strongly inspired Child-Computer Interaction (CCI) research, in which children have been positioned as a participant group that has a right to have a voice and a say when designing digital technology for them, with the development of ways by which to enable children to exercise this right with an equal footing to adults [7, 18].

When we design something, we engage in world making and world changing – hence, design is a form of futures making as articulated in PD. To be able to explore alternatives and to make a change, we need to imagine what the change could be. For creating a better future, there is also a need to understand that futures are rooted in the past and present. In addition to discussions in PD, in design research there has emerged a strong interest in speculative and critical design, devoted to imagining different futures (e.g., [8]). Ylipulli and Vigren [36] building on PD as well as speculative and critical design traditions, argue for engaging citizens in “active future-making”. Along similar lines, CCI researchers have started engaging children in envisioning, debating, and critiquing alternative, utopian, dystopian, or desirable digital futures [34]. To be able and willing to engage in futures making, one needs transformative agency [17]. Recent CCI research emphasizes fostering children’s

computational empowerment (CE), which involves developing their ability to understand digital technology and its societal impacts, and to engage critically and curiously with its construction and deconstruction [6, 19]. Transformative agency is central to this, as it highlights children’s ability to approach the world critically yet constructively and to transform the acquired knowledge into action geared at improving their own matters, shared matters, or even societal issues, for a better and more just society [16].

In education, there has been a turn to design during the last decade [5], with approaches like design thinking [23], as well as views presenting teaching as design [11, 26] gaining popularity. Simultaneously, scholars have increasingly advocated for embracing participatory approaches to amplify students’ voices [32]. Successful initiatives can be found in children’s computing education within CCI research, where PD has been adopted to leverage CE [6]. In the context of citizenship, scholars have argued for seeing design as “performing citizenship” [1]. CCI scholars’ work has intersected with citizenship education, contributing to this field by designing tools for children’s civic participation [20, 22, 33], and proposing approaches that merge design and participation [17, 37]. Despite these contributions, however, there is no clear articulation of how PD can contribute to citizenship education. While studies show how children can drive change and address injustice, they do not elaborate how PD can become an intrinsic part of citizenship education. This is the line of research we pursue further.

Building on well-accepted approaches to citizenship education (see [10, 15]), we define Design Citizenship as the understanding of one’s role as a designer within society, promoting active and inclusive participation in shaping shared matters, and encouraging thoughtful consideration of the rights, responsibilities, and ethical implications tied to the act of designing for the public good. We argue that design citizenship – embracing Scandinavian PD principles, design as futures making, and transformative agency – should be integrated into children’s citizenship education. We believe the concept of Design Citizenship is a powerful tool for cultivating democratic cultures.

3 Illustrations from case projects

We draw from six studies involving workshops with children to illustrate different ways to cultivate Design Citizenship in learning environments (Table 1). Strategies for scaffolding Design Citizenship have been built in the workshops: positioning children as genuine participants in critiquing the present day and dreaming of alternative futures, and fostering their transformative agency to make a change through various activism-oriented methods; all this aiming to show them there is hope for better futures.

3.1 Scandinavian PD Principles

Scandinavian PD principles have been integral to our design practices with children. From the current paper’s perspective, the most relevant principles are discussed below. They have shaped our methods choices regarding scaffolding children’s Design Citizenship; they encourage and scaffold the mindset of genuine and active participation on an everyday basis, which should be at the core of citizenship education (i.e., they promote active and inclusive participation in shaping shared environments and systems):

Table 1: Case workshops

Study id	Study topic	Context and aim of the workshops (formal/non-formal education)	Methods used to scaffold design citizenship
"1	Everyday democracy in social media	12-14-year-olds (formal). Promoting daily democracy through children's involvement as co-researchers, investigating social media issues and seeking alternatives, linked with technology education. See also Figure 1 for an example of methods used in the project.	Critiquing the present day through thematic analysis and mind maps of youth-led social media auto-ethnographies. Designing novel social media concepts for cultivating relations based on well-being and mutual care.
"2, "3	Technology use practices in everyday life	10-11-year-olds (formal, technology education), and 15-17-year-olds (non-formal, summer traineeship linked with an AI Ambassadorship program). Cultivating children's transformational agency in relation to digital technology through children examining digital technology past, present, and future use.	Technology use history timelines for understanding past and its link to today. Analyzing current technology use for critiquing the present day. Dreaming about alternative futures through imagining solutions to the problems.
"4	Critical design and making	11-12-year-olds (formal, a number of different school subjects). Exploring the problem of designing and evaluating antibullying prototypes, and mobilizing others for action taking against bullying, envisioning bullying free digital futures.	Letter writing and miracle discussions for critiquing the present day. Design fiction, miracle discussions, and dystopian and utopian scenarios for dreaming about alternative futures. Theatre of the oppressed for fostering making a change.
"5	Envisioning social justice in datafied societies	15-17-year-olds (non-formal, summer traineeship linked with an AI Ambassadorship program). Fostering critical reflection on AI ethical challenges, encouraging participants to envision alternatives contributing to inclusive, justice-oriented societies.	Understanding and critiquing the present day through personas based on various data profiles. Futures Headlines and desirable futures visions for dreaming about alternative futures. Theatre of the oppressed for challenging data injustices and exploring how a justice-oriented datafied society might look like.
"6	Transformative agency and emerging technologies for social good	14-15-year-olds (formal, technology education). Critically exploring current conflict laden situations, children's agency within, the potential of emerging technologies for good and for bad, and different ways by which children can try to change the world for the better.	Cultural probes, conflict of motives analysis for critiquing the present day. Critical technology exploration and reflection on their consequences, advertisement and warning video production for dreaming about alternative futures. Design activism for fostering making a change.

Participation itself, i.e., giving voice and say to children, has been emphasized in all our projects. We have invited children to design solutions to problems meaningful to them and enabled them to make an impact and be heard in broader contexts. This includes theatre of the oppressed performances ("4, "5), activism campaigns in their schools ("6), public exhibitions of their work ("1), creating logos and taglines to catch others' attention to important issues ("2, "3), and supporting them to become leaders and organize their own events ("5, "6). Our goal has been to show them that their voice matters and others are interested in what they have to say.

Valuing everybody's skills and fostering mutual reciprocal learning. In all studies, the methods selected have helped children learn from each other and adults, while also making it explicit that adults also learned from children. For instance, positioning children as co-researchers ("1); encouraging them to value diverse knowledge systems within their groups and take collective action – they have been collaborating in teams, listening to each other, making

decisions together about what topics to work on, giving constructive feedback to each other ("1 - "6); and even participating in others' contributions such as in the Theater of the Oppressed plays ("4, "5); have been concrete strategies embedded in our methodological choices. At times, this learning process has spanned a longer period, with children and various adults collaboratively refining the design solutions ("4).

Equalizing power relations. In line with CCI practices, we have aimed in all our projects to empower children to shape their own matters but also broader community or societal matters, and in relation to adults who typically hold more power. In some projects there has been a specific focus on problematic power relations, such as bullying and discrimination ("1, "4, "5). Transversal to all studies has been the emphasis in supporting children to define and focus on everyday matters that are relevant to them in their own terms.

3.2 Design as Futures Making

The core of design futures activities is the belief that many futures are possible and actively constructed through present decisions. In our projects, children have been encouraged to consider 'what if' questions about current issues. For instance, in "1 and "4, they identified various forms of violence in their everyday life or social media. To scaffold their understanding of one's role as a designer within society, able to cultivate hope for themselves and for others, they collected evidence and/or examined problems from various perspectives, and collectively envisioned alternative social media futures or bullying free futures. All workshops emphasized challenging the current state through imaginations expressed through scenarios ("1 - "6) and prototypes ("4, "6), not just envisioning technological futures, but imagining the futures they want to live in. All cases have been characterized by the plurality of designs and ideas produced by children. This has helped to convey the idea that rather than "ultimate solutions", what is truly needed are "alternatives". These multiple alternatives towards "better", "desirable" futures are crucial for democracy as they fuel critical conversations about the futures we want to be part of.

3.3 Supporting Children's Transformative Agency

Children have been invited as change makers to consider alternative digital futures in all our projects, promoting their active participation in shaping better environments and systems. Some projects have focused on discussing and reflecting on their experiences and interest in activism ("4,"5, "6). Several projects have invited children to select issues they feel strongly about in their everyday lives ("1 - "4, "6).

We have engaged children in critically examining the status quo, focusing on inequality and oppression ("4 - "6), and taking action to create change using design and digital technology ("1 - "6). Children have participated collectively and with adults ("4), considering what issues they can solve alone and what requires collaboration with others ("2, "3). This understanding of agency and power has broadened their thinking about what counts as participation and the skills, allies, and resources needed for everyday societal participation. We see these activities as scaffolding children's thoughtful consideration of the rights, responsibilities, and ethical implications of designing for the public good.

4 Concluding discussion

We contribute by proposing the notion of Design Citizenship, to cultivate democratic cultures in citizenship education across formal and non-formal learning environments. With this, we advocate for the conscious use of PD in children's citizenship education. Our projects demonstrate how citizenship education can be embedded in design projects, using Scandinavian PD principles and critical, futures design methods to examine past, present, and future, serving as backbones for practices that cultivate democratic cultures.

Following Biesta [2], we believe that participatory democracy is learned through participation. Radical democracy emphasizes the need to actively construct and nurture democratic practices on an everyday basis. Education for democracy should be embodied and experiential. Children and youth need to engage in tackling relevant

challenges with different others to learn about democracy and civic participation, as we have done in our projects. This approach helps them understand the possibilities, challenges, and limitations, but also the rewards of co-building participatory democratic cultures.

In a time of societal polarization and "democracy without rights," Design Citizenship offers hope by encouraging citizens to see the world as designable and changeable. Now more than ever, we need educational approaches that inspire collective dreaming rather than individual survival, especially for children facing online phobic forces against gender, sexual identity, and racial diversity. We believe fostering a design mindset helps envision alternatives and recognize multiple options and ways of doing. Design Citizenship allows people to focus on desired futures and take action to shape them, highlighting design's power to guide behavior, identify flaws in the current world, and drive societal change. It also includes digital literacy, teaching children to design and change the world together with diverse others. While the concept of Design Citizenship needs further elaboration for practical implementation in various educational settings, we seek to join forces with scholars and educators addressing similar issues in computing and citizenship education to envision pedagogies of hope.

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